

ANALYSIS OF THE STORIES "SUMBUL" AND "INVITATION" BY SAID AHMAD

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Abstract. *The article describes the changes in the human psyche in the most complex and conflicting environment, the universe and man. serious attention was paid to the interpretation of human and human relations. Attention was paid to the fact that the story with a different tone is interpreted in the context of human tragedies, conflicts in the social environment, and changes in the personal psyche in an opposing dialectical unity. The complexity of the politics of the dead period, personal will and freedom, justice and injustice, the expression of heroes who became victims of right and wrong were expressed in different angles.*

Keywords: *spirit, artistry, interpretation, person, concept, environment, character.*

A real human tragedy is described in the story "Taklifnoma" from the collection of stories "Karako'z Majnun". While reading this story, as A. Qahhor noted, "If the writer writes about something he does not feel, the reader who reads it cannot feel anything either. Therefore, it is necessary to burn in order to burn, and to honor in order to honor...".

The hero of the story is a real person in a new era. He participated in the Great Patriotic War. Tragedy falls on him like a natural disaster. So, is this a "little man" who fell under the wheel of history? Not at all. That's not the point. The hero of the story, Shafyor Bekmurodov, is imprisoned for two years for a small crime and is separated from his beloved wife. While he is in prison, his wife is in trouble: the man who promised to save her husband cheats her in the worst way.

"When Bekmurodov returned from prison, he saw the child born in his absence. The storyteller reveals the most complex gammas of the hero's experiences. At first, he is shaken by unbridled anger, when he learns the cause of the tragedy, he is surrounded by a feeling of grief and helplessness, a severe internal conflict occurs between his love and passion for his wife and his instinctive attitude towards her and the child. But humanity does it physically. He stays at home. Trying to heal his wife's spiritual ignorance, he shows all the beauty of courage, love and nobility."

He tries to forget the incident and does not hurt his wife. But the burden of this test weighs heavily on his wife. He closed his eyes, leaving behind a three-year-old girl. The death of Bekmurodov's wife is the climax of the story. A woman crushed by her misfortune forgets what happiness is. Even her husband's love and devotion cannot bring a smile to her face. When she saw Bekmurodov taking care of the child, a smile appeared in the eyes of the woman lying on her deathbed.

The writer does not force his attitude on the characters; does not judge their behavior; they determine the flow of events only with short remarks. But the hero of the story is revealed not as a "little man", but as a big man who has preserved his humanity even in the midst of all life's difficulties. In this humanity of the hero, not only the universal humanistic aspects of the character, but also the socialist quality are revealed. The hero of Said Ahmed is a man of today. It

is not a sum of certain qualities and characteristics, but a whole human personality. Nationality is manifested in a complex unity. Bekmurodov's feelings are legitimate for any person, especially for an oriental man. Bekmurodov's feelings as a new person lead in overcoming the power of age-old traditions. Bekmurodov did not look for the murderer, he refused to punish the villain who separated from the person he loved and threatened his life. Vahobjon and Gulsum met many times in Sumbulsoy. They were staring at each other with their loving hearts. But such a secret could not be kept in a small village.

Somehow, during one of their meetings in Sumbulsoi, four or five young men ambushed them and caught them in Sumbulsoi. They let the girl go and took Vahobjon to the village. They put black on their faces and drive them out of the village. In the desert, the hand of Vahobjon, who was riding upside down on a donkey, was untied by the old shepherd, who took pity on him and took him out on his horse to the Denov road.

In the story, Vahobjon and Gulsum's mental struggles are similar to Bekmurodov's situation. The heroes of both stories express their spiritual aspirations in their hearts and souls.

In the works of the writer, the expression of the spiritual aspirations of a person, the interpretation of his tragic destiny in the path of a difficult and difficult life are expressed. The interpretation of spiritual aspirations leads in all the works of the writer, there are also views of the integral unity with the interpretation of the destiny of the individual.

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